

Measuring the Mechanical Properties of Fibre Reinforced Hydrogels Using Volume Controlled Cavitation

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1. Objective

The objective of this study is to investigate the capability of volume-controlled cavitation rheology to quantitatively characterize the mechanical properties of fiber-reinforced polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) hydrogels. While cavitation rheology has traditionally been applied to isotropic soft materials, its applicability to anisotropic systems—such as gels reinforced with aligned fiber structures—remains underexplored. By preparing both solid and fiber-reinforced hydrogel samples and subjecting them to localized internal pressurization, we aim to:

- Examine how embedded polyester threads affect the local mechanical response of hydrogels,
- Fit the resulting pressure–stretch data using both isotropic (Yeoh) and anisotropic, Holzapfel-Gasser-Ogden (HGO) constitutive model,
- Determine whether the anisotropic fiber contribution extracted from uniaxial tensile testing can be used to accurately reconstruct the full composite response observed via cavitation rheology.

This work seeks to validate cavitation rheology as a robust tool for probing the integrated matrix–fiber mechanics of structurally engineered soft materials under complex deformation fields.

2. Samples Preparation

2.1. Materials

Poly(vinyl alcohol) (PVA; Product No. 378321, Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, MO, USA), with an average molecular weight of ~89,000–98,000 and ≥99% hydrolysis, was used as the primary polymer. Glycerol (Product No. G7893, Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, MO, USA) served as a plasticizer to enhance the transparency and flexibility of the hydrogel. Deionized (DI) water was used as the solvent throughout the preparation process.

Cubic molds with internal dimensions of 30 mm × 30 mm × 30 mm were fabricated using a stereolithography (SLA) 3D printer (Form 3, Formlabs Inc., Somerville, MA, USA). For the preparation of reinforced samples, the mold design was modified to include regularly spaced perforations to allow the integration of tensioned polyester threads within the hydrogel matrix (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. 3D printed molds

2.2. Hydrogels

Polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) hydrogels were prepared by mixing PVA (Merck, 67.04 g) with glycerin (26.6 mL) and deionized (DI) water (33.52 mL) to achieve a 5:5 PVA-to-glycerin ratio by weight, with glycerin included to enhance the optical transparency of the final hydrogel. The total liquid phase (glycerin + DI water) amounted to 60.12 g, resulting in a polymer concentration of approximately 52.7% w/w relative to the liquid phase.

The mixing procedure followed the protocol outlined by Nafo and Al-Mayah [1], which ensures uniform dissolution of PVA into the glycerin–water mixture through a high-temperature stirring cycle. The solution was heated and stirred until fully homogenized and clear, indicating complete dissolution of the PVA.

Two types of samples were prepared from the resulting solution. For Sample 1 (unreinforced), the hydrogel solution was cast into a cubic mold with internal dimensions of 30 mm × 30 mm × 30 mm and allowed to cool to room temperature. For Sample 2 (reinforced), a similar mold was modified with specialized perforations to accommodate polyester thread lines (diameter: 0.2 mm) arranged in parallel and spaced 0.2 mm apart. The threads were tensioned and extended across the gel volume to reinforce the hydrogel matrix (see Figure 2 for reinforcement layout). Three replicates were fabricated for each sample type to ensure consistency and reproducibility of the measurements.

Figure 2. Solid and Reinforced gels

All samples were physically crosslinked using a single freeze–thaw cycle, in which gels were frozen at $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 3 hours and then thawed to room temperature. This process induced the formation of crystalline domains within the PVA network, yielding stable hydrogel structures suitable for mechanical testing.

2.3. Cavitation rheology

Cavity expansion tests were performed to characterize the local mechanical response of the PVA hydrogels using a custom injection system. A 6800 Series Universal Testing System (Instron, Norwood, MA, USA) was used to precisely control the injection displacement rate. The injection medium consisted of deionized (DI) water mixed with brilliant blue FCF dye (FD&C Blue No. 1), a commonly used water-soluble colorant, to facilitate visual tracking of cavity formation during testing.

A 10 mL syringe filled with the dyed DI water was mounted vertically on the Instron machine. The syringe was connected via high-pressure tubing to a stainless steel needle (outer diameter: 1.0 mm) which featured a custom-drilled lateral shaft hole (diameter: 0.9 mm) located 1 mm from the needle tip. The distal tip of the needle was sealed using a high-strength, water-resistant epoxy adhesive (Araldite® Rapid, Huntsman Advanced Materials) to prevent flow through the terminal opening. This design allowed fluid to exit solely through the side port, reducing the need for retraction procedures that are commonly used to nucleate cavities and minimizing disruption to the surrounding gel matrix.

The needle was inserted into the midpoint of the gel specimen along the vertical axis, ensuring a centrally located initial cavity site. Fluid was injected at a constant volumetric rate of 33 $\mu\text{L/s}$. The injection pressure was monitored in real-time using an inline pressure transducer (Model PRESS-S-000, PendoTECH, Princeton, NJ, USA) placed between the syringe and the needle. The sensor output was recorded using pressure reader (Model PMAT-S, Pendo Tech, USA). All tests were performed at room temperature ($\sim 22^\circ\text{C}$), and care was taken to avoid pre-loading or perturbing the gel structure during needle insertion. Figure 3 illustrate the test set up.

Figure 3. Test set up

2.4. Tensile test

Tensile tests were performed on the polyester threads used for hydrogel reinforcement to evaluate their uniaxial mechanical response under low strain rate conditions. The same universal testing machine employed in the cavity expansion tests (6800 Series Universal Testing System, Instron, Norwood, MA, USA) was used for this purpose. A custom-designed

fixture was mounted onto the test frame to secure and align the thread specimens during testing (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Tensile test set up

Each thread sample, dyed red for visibility, was cut to a gauge length of 50 mm and clamped between two 3D-printed circular grips. The grips were fabricated to ensure minimal slippage and uniform distribution of stress along the thread. Lateral tightening screws and a C-clamp were used to stabilize the fixture and maintain coaxial alignment throughout the test.

The tests were conducted at room temperature ($\sim 22\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$). Axial tensile loading was applied at a controlled strain rate of 0.05 s^{-1} until failure. The strain rate was selected to mimic quasi-static conditions and prevent dynamic artifacts in the stress–strain response. Load and extension data were recorded continuously through the Instron’s integrated Bluehill software platform. Prior to testing, the system was calibrated to ensure zero preload on the sample and to eliminate compliance-related effects in the grips and machine frame.

Each measurement was repeated for three thread specimens to ensure statistical reproducibility. The resulting stress–strain curves were used to quantify the tensile modulus and the failure strain of the threads.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Cavitation test

Cavitation rheology revealed distinct differences in the mechanical response of solid and reinforced PVA hydrogels under internal pressurization. The pressure–hoop stretch (λ) curves for both sample types (Figure 5a) showed a non-linear increase in cavity pressure with increasing deformation, consistent with the expected behavior of soft, hyperelastic materials. Notably, the reinforced gel exhibited consistently higher pressure values across the entire stretch range compared to the unreinforced solid gel, indicating a stiffening effect induced by the embedded polyester threads.

To characterize the hyperelastic behavior of the gels, the experimental data were used to calibrate the Yeoh strain energy model, employing the derivative form of the radial stress with respect to hoop stretch, given by:

$$\frac{dP}{d\lambda} = \frac{\widehat{W}}{\lambda^3 - 1} \quad (1)$$

where \widehat{W} denotes the strain energy density function. Calibration was conducted following the protocol described by Nafu and Al-Mayah [1], yielding excellent agreement between the model and experimental data for both gel types ($R^2 = 0.999$ for each case, Figure 5b).

Figure 5. a) The pressure–hoop stretch (λ) curves; b) calibration process.

The fitted material parameters for the solid gel are summarized in table 1

Table1. Calibrated material parameters

Material parameters	Solid Gel	Reinforced Gel
C_{10} (MPa)	0.0076	0.0192
C_{20} (MPa)	0.0125	0.0251
C_{30} (MPa)	0.00092	0.00135

These results indicate a marked increase in all three Yeoh parameters in the presence of reinforcement, suggesting enhanced resistance to volumetric deformation and nonlinear stiffening behavior.

The critical cavity pressure, defined as the peak pressure prior to unstable cavity expansion, was higher in the reinforced gel (0.07 MPa) compared to the solid gel (0.058 MPa), as shown in Figure 6. Correspondingly, the initial Young's modulus (E), estimated using $E = 6C_{10}$, was 0.0455 MPa for the solid gel and increased to 0.115 MPa for the reinforced gel. This near 2.5-fold increase further substantiates the effectiveness of thread reinforcement in enhancing the gel's local stiffness.

Figure 6. Critical pressure values and Young's modulus

Taken together, these findings confirm that fiber reinforcement significantly alters the local mechanical environment within the hydrogel. The improved cavity resistance and stiffness may be attributed to mechanical coupling between the matrix and embedded threads, which likely redistribute stresses and constrain localized deformation around the expanding cavity.

3.2. Tensile test

The tensile mechanical behavior of the polyester threads used for reinforcing the PVA gels was characterized under uniaxial loading conditions. Figure 4 presents the force–displacement response obtained from three replicate tests conducted at a strain rate of 0.05 s^{-1} , with a gauge length of 50 mm. The experiments were performed using the same universal testing machine (Instron 6800 Series, Instron, Norwood, MA, USA) described in the cavity expansion setup.

The threads demonstrated a nonlinear, progressive stiffening behavior across the displacement range. At small extensions (0–10 mm), the force increased gradually, corresponding to the low-stiffness toe region commonly observed in polymeric fibers, likely due to straightening of the thread's microstructure and reorientation of molecular chains. Beyond ~15 mm of displacement, the load–extension curve steepened, indicating increased axial stiffness with elongation. The maximum recorded force approached 8.7 N at a displacement of 50 mm, with low variability across samples, as shown by the error bars in Figure 4.

Figure 7. Tensile test data of polyester threads.

The absence of abrupt force drops throughout the test suggests that the polyester threads maintained structural integrity and did not exhibit premature yielding or fiber rupture within the tested displacement range. This behavior supports their role as reliable reinforcements capable of sustaining tensile loads when embedded within the hydrogel matrix.

4. Data Analysis: Validating Cavitation Rheology for Fiber-Reinforced Gels

To evaluate the ability of cavitation rheology to characterize the mechanical behavior of fiber-reinforced hydrogels, we analyzed the hoop stress response predicted from spherical cavity expansion using two different constitutive frameworks: the Yeoh model (for isotropic fits) and the Holzapfel–Gasser–Ogden (HGO) model (for anisotropic fiber-reinforced behavior).

The reinforced gel was initially treated as isotropic for fitting purposes, and the corresponding pressure–stretch data were used to calibrate the Yeoh strain energy function:

$$W = C_{10}(I_1 - 3) + C_{20}(I_1 - 3)^2 + C_{30}(I_1 - 3)^3 \quad (2)$$

with fitted parameters:

$$C_{10} = 0.0192 \text{ MPa}, C_{20} = 0.0251 \text{ MPa}, C_{30} = 0.00135 \text{ MPa}.$$

From this, the initial shear modulus was estimated as $\mu = 2C_{10} = 0.0384 \text{ MPa}$. Using the derived hoop stress expression for the Yeoh model under spherical expansion, the predicted stress–stretch behavior is shown in Figure 8 (dashed line), demonstrating a nonlinear increase in stress consistent with experimental observations.

Figure 8. Yeoh model Hoops stress vs Hoop stretch

To more accurately reflect the anisotropic nature of the reinforced hydrogel, we then constructed an HGO model that combines the solid matrix (modeled using the Yeoh parameters from the solid, unreinforced gel) with an additional fiber contribution aligned in the hoop direction. The total hoop stress was computed as:

$$\sigma_{\theta} = \mu(\lambda^2 - \lambda^{-4}) + 2k_1(\lambda^2 - 1)\lambda^2 * \exp [k_2(\lambda^2 - 1)^2] \quad (3)$$

To isolate the fiber mechanics, the anisotropic term was calibrated using the experimental stress–stretch data from the uniaxial tensile tests on the polyester threads. Fitting yielded the fiber-related parameters:

$k_1 = 0.18$ MPa; $k_2 = 0.002$

As shown in Figure 9, where the HGO fit closely follows the stress–stretch curve of the threads.

Figure 9. Calibration of the material parameters of the anisotropic term of HGO model.

Substituting the obtained parameters into the full HGO hoop stress formulation yielded the predicted hoop stress behavior in reinforced gels. As shown in Figure 10, there was excellent

agreement between the HGO-based hoop stress prediction and the Yeoh model fitted to the reinforced gel data. This match validates that the mechanics captured by cavitation rheology, under localized deformation, are consistent with the underlying fiber-reinforced structure, and that the HGO model provides a mechanistically grounded framework that bridges the local matrix and fiber contributions.

Figure 10. HGO-hoop stress vs Yeoh-hoop stress of fiber-reinforced hydrogels.

These results demonstrate that cavitation rheology can effectively resolve both isotropic and anisotropic components of soft hydrogel systems, making it a powerful tool for characterizing engineered and biologically inspired materials with internal reinforcement structures.

5. Conclusion:

This study demonstrates that volume-controlled cavitation rheology is a powerful technique for assessing the local mechanical properties of fiber-reinforced hydrogels, including both isotropic and anisotropic material contributions. The pressure–stretch behavior of PVA hydrogels with and without embedded polyester threads revealed that fiber reinforcement leads to a clear increase in local stiffness and cavity resistance. The use of the Yeoh model provided an effective isotropic fit to the reinforced gel data, while the anisotropic response was more accurately captured by the HGO model.

By calibrating the isotropic matrix response using parameters derived from the unreinforced gel and the anisotropic fiber term from tensile tests on the polyester threads, we successfully reconstructed the composite hoop stress response observed in cavitation tests. The strong agreement between the Yeoh and HGO predictions reinforces the validity of cavitation rheology as a quantitative method for characterizing the integrated behavior of reinforced soft materials.

Overall, this work establishes a framework for using localized cavitation mechanics to probe and model fiber–matrix interactions in hydrogels and similar soft composites, with potential applications in biomaterials, soft robotics, and tissue engineering.

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References

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